

Synthesis of *N*-Mannich Bases of 5(6)-Phenoxybenzimidazole and 5-(4-Chlorophenoxy)benzimidazolin-2-thione as Potential Biologically Active Agents

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5(6)-Phenoxybenzimidazole (1) has been synthesised by reaction of 4-phenoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine and formic acid, while 5-(4-chlorophenoxy)benzimidazolin-2-thione (2) has been synthesised by reaction of 4-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*o*-phenylenediamine and CS₂, in presence of ethanolic KOH. The compounds 1 and 2 when subjected to Mannich reaction with various anilines gave 5(6)-phenoxy-1-arylaminomethylbenzimidazoles (1a-e) and 1,3-bis(arylaminomethyl)-5-(4-chlorophenoxy)benzimidazolin-2-thiones (2a-h). The compounds thus synthesised were investigated for their antiviral activity against TMV and CGMMV. Most of the compounds showed significant antiviral activity.

BENZIMIDAZOLES have been reported to possess wide range of biological responses, such as antibacterial¹, antifungal², antiviral^{3,4}, anthelmintic⁵, insecticidal⁶ and herbicidal⁷. In view of these reports it was considered of interest to synthesise the title compounds and to evaluate their antiviral activity against TMV and CGMMV.

The synthesis of 5(6)-phenoxybenzimidazole (1) was achieved by the reaction of 4-phenoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine and formic acid. 1 was also synthesised by Phillip's method⁸. For the synthesis of the title products (1a-e), 1 was treated with 40% aqueous formaldehyde solution and various anilines under the condition of Mannich reaction (Scheme 1).

R = H, Cl, Br, OH, OCH₃

Scheme 1

The synthesis of 5-(4-chlorophenoxy)benzimidazolin-2-thione (2) was achieved by the reaction of 4-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*o*-phenylenediamine and CS₂ in presence of ethanolic KOH. For the synthesis of the title products (2a-h), 2 was treated with HCHO and various anilines under the condition of Mannich reaction (Scheme 2). All the synthesised compounds

R = H, Cl, Br, OH, OCH₃, NO₂, COOCH₃, COOH, H

Scheme 2

were characterised by elemental analyses and spectral data.

The mass spectrum of 1a exhibited ions peaks at *m/z* 210, 203, 152, 133, 105, 104, 77 and 51, but molecular ion peak was not observed.

The mass spectrum of compounds 2a did not display molecular ion peak but exhibited ion peaks at *m/z* 276/278, 165, 137, 105, 104, 77 and 51 in conformity with the structure.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer in KBr and the characteristic bands are given in Tables 1 and 2. The nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Varian A-60D spectrometer and the characteristic signals are given in Tables 1 and 2. The mass spectra were obtained on a Hitachi RMV-6 instrument at 70 eV.

TABLE 1—ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITY OF 5(6)-PHENOXY-1-ARYLAMINOMETHYLBENZIMIDAZOLES (1a-e)*

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p.** °C	% Inhibition of TMV/D.s.**		% Inhibition of CGMMV/C.a.**	
				<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>	<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>
1	—	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	180	66	46	63	58
1a	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O	160	65	56	63	57
1b	Cl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O	145	57	49	55	48
1c	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O	155	54	45	45	45
1d	OH	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	188	48	51	51	36
1e	OCH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ .H ₂ O	142	58	31	49	46

* All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses : yield, 40-50%.

** Recrystallised from methanol. $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1, 3100 (NH), 1590 (C=N), 1140 (C-O-C); 1e, 8300 (NH), 1600 (C=N), 1120 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C).

** D. s = *Datura stramonium*, C. a = *Chenopodium amaranticolor*.

TABLE 2—1,3-BIS(ARYLAMINOMETHYL)-5-(4-CHLOROPHENOXY)BENZIMIDAZOLIN-2-THIONES (2a-h)*

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p.** °C	% Inhibition of TMV/ <i>Datura stramonium</i>		% Inhibition of CGMMV/ <i>Chenopodium amaranticolor</i>	
				<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>	<i>In vitro</i>	<i>In vivo</i>
2a	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ ClN ₄ OS	74	55	29	51	45
2b	Cl	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	70	58	45	37	30
2c	Br	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ BrClN ₄ OS	90	55	48	39	40
2d	OH	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ OS	86	60	47	48	50
2e	OCH ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	87	63	44	52	50
2f	NH ₂	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ ClN ₅ O ₂ S	225	74	65	66	63
2g	COOCH ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	195	7	NH	15	15
2h	COOCH ₂ H ₅	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ ClN ₄ O ₃ S	180	23	17	36	31

* All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses ; yield, 45-55%.

** The compounds were recrystallised from CHCl₃ and petroleum ether (60-80°). $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2a, 8400 (NH), 1220 (C=S), 1100 (C-O-C); 2g, 8350 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1190 (C=S), 1105 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). δ (CDCl₃) 2d, 2.1 (6H, CH₃), 5.5 (4H, N-CH₂-N) and 6.7-7.3 (17H, aromatic and NH proton).

5(6)-Phenoxybenzimidazole (1) :

Method A. A mixture of 4-phenoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine (10 g, 0.05 mol) and 90% formic acid (5 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 2 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was basified with 10% NaOH. The crude product thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol, (70%).

Method B : 1 was also prepared by utilising Phillips method⁹. 4-Phenoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine (10 g) and formic acid (5 ml) were taken in 4 N HCl (50 ml), and boiled for 1 h under reflux. The contents were then filtered and cold filtrate was neutralised with ammonia. The crude product was recrystallised from methanol, (65%).

5(6)-Phenoxy-1-arylaminomethylbenzimidazoles (1a-e) : To 1 (1 g) in methanol (10 ml) formalin (0.5 ml) and an appropriate amine (0.005 mol) were added. The mixture was heated for 10 min on a water-bath. The product separated on scratching the sides of the flask, was recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

5-(4-Chlorophenoxy)benzimidazolin-2-thione (2) : 4-(4-Chlorophenoxy)-*o*-phenylenediamine (10 g) was dissolved in methanol (45 ml) and diluted with water (10 ml). KOH (3 g) and CS₂ (4 ml) were added to it and the contents were refluxed for 2 h and then filtered hot. The filtrate was acidified

with 10% acetic acid. The solid obtained was recrystallised from methanol to yield the product (80%), m.p. 250° (lit⁵. 251°).

1,3-Bis(arylaminomethyl)-5-(4-chlorophenoxy)benzimidazolin-2-thiones (2a-h) : To 2 (0.7 g) in methanol (10 ml), formalin (1 ml) and an appropriate amine (0.005 mol) were added with stirring. The reaction mixture was warmed on a water-bath for 1 min. The product was separated by allowing the reaction mixture to stand at room temperature overnight.

Antiviral activity :

All of compound were evaluated for antiviral activity against TMV and CGMMV both *in vitro* and *in vivo* by the method of Verma *et al.*⁹.

Antiviral activity against tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) : The culture of TMV was maintained by successive host inoculation (*Datura stramonium* plants). The compounds were dissolved in their respective solvents. The solutions were termed 'test solution'. The percentage of inhibition was expressed as, % inhibition = (C - T)/C × 100, where C = number of lesions on control leaves, and T = number of lesions on treated leaves. It is evident that most of the compounds have shown significant activity against TMV *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Tables 1 and 2).

Antiviral activity against cucumber green mottle mosaic virus (CGMMV): The culture of CGMMV was maintained by successive host inoculation (*Chenopodium amaranticolor* plants). It is evident that most of the compounds have exhibited significant inhibition against CGMMV *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Tables 1 and 2).

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